

THE RELATIONS BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND THE EUROPEAN UNION DURING THE 30 YEARS

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Abstract: *Uzbekistan and European Union relations has achieved great success during the past 30 years. Cooperation and partnership between both regions include in many fields, such as in the economic relations, the turnover increase year by year, while in the social and cultural cooperation as well as exchange educational programs have increased. Both countries try to build bridges in terms of rule of law, like protecting human rights, as well as connectivity of political and cultural relations. In order to establish these programs and continue partnership EU and Uzbekistan representatives discussed and exchange ideas between them in many conferences.*

Key word: *Cooperation, economically, politicly, human rights, democratization, turnover, geostrategic, solar energy, Central Asia, European Union, during and after the pandemic, cultural and educational exchange programs.*

The relations between the European Union and Uzbekistan have started after that time, when the twelve member countries of the EU recognized the state independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan and on December 31, 1991, signed a document entitled "Joint Declaration of the Twelve". Diplomatic relations between the two regions were established on November 16, 1994.

During the past 30 years the European Union has been the largest trade and aid partner of Central Asia, in particular Uzbekistan, after signed the Agreement on Cooperation and Partnership. Currently, they are co-organizing in the deepening infrastructure and energy sector.

In addition, Uzbekistan has established partnerships with the EU in many spheres, such as in education and economic reform, as well as political rule of law and democratization. For example, in 2016, this is worth to emphasize that, Fredrick Carlar, a senior of EIAS official, said about the relations between EU and five Central Asian countries setting new goals for bilateral and regional cooperation in terms of economic, social, political and cultural relations had reached a new level since 2017. In order to expand interconnectivity, for instance, the European Union has been able to reach some of its ambitious goals through projects like "Central Asia invest" - which aims at developing SMEs (small and medium-sized

enterprises) in the country - or TRACECA (Transport Corridor for Europe Caucasus and Asia).

In terms of economic cooperation, the European Union remains Central Asia's largest trading partner, with a trade turnover of 1 billion euros in previous years. Share of Uzbekistan in imports amounted to 21,5 %, while exports reached to 8,5% between 2017 and 2020. During the corona virus of covid 19, imports fell by 0,0 % and exports by 0,1 % of Uzbekistan. However, after the pandemic situation, this figure increased dramatically, such as imports of Uzbekistan amounted 138,6 % and exports to 3,0 %.

According to statistics in 2021, the total volume of imports between the European Union and Uzbekistan was grown by € 476, and exports by €2,292.

From European Union countries, especially Germany is one of the main trade and economic partner of Uzbekistan in Europe. This partnership is particularly in technology and investment. Germany has a special place in the nations' economic and cultural cooperation with the EU and Uzbekistan. In 2017, the Uzbek-German trade turnover amounted to 613,2 million US dollars. From January to November in 2018, it has achieved to 712,1 million US dollars. In 2019, this figure reached 1 billion euros. The total volume of financial and technical cooperation between the two states exceeds 329,9 million euros.

Geopolitically and strategically, Central Asia is also a great importance for the EU. The region has a large amount of gas and oil reserves, which attract major international partners. As an example of that, the natural conditions and resources of Uzbekistan, increase the possibility of obtaining solar energy as a result of almost 300 sunny days a year.

In order to build bridges between Uzbekistan and EU, political and international relation specialists of Uzbekistan and of the European Union, exchange ideas in terms of strategy and challenges of Central Asia, such as hard situations of Afghanistan and its impact to border countries. They also pointed out about the regional cooperation, especially in the field of economic and education. For example, both state members discussed about the benefits of student and education programs in order to continue and boost their partnership further.

However, it should be noted that no matter of how with effort of these projects are launched, Russia and China play a huge role due to their economic and political influence. For example, Uzbekistan-China relations has the potential to develop to have spillover effect in the long-term. Moreover, Uzbek-China trade turnover was approximately 3,25 billion US dollars, whereas the volume of Uzbekistan- Russia trade turnover was around 2,7 billion US dollars in 2015. Volume of Chinese investments and loans in Uzbekistan is around 5,5 billion US dollars and currently

there are over 600 enterprises with Chinese capital that are operating in the country.

However, I believe that Central Asia, especially Uzbekistan, is interested in and seeks ways to develop cooperation and partnership with the European Union. This is due to the fact that the EU is trying not only to stabilize the economy of Uzbekistan in terms of the agroindustry, like rise the agriculture, but also it turn into an industrialized country and in this area achieved many developments.

In addition, bringing cooperation with Erasmus+ and Horizon 2020 to a higher level may be due to a number of achievements in the spheres of the rule of law, human rights and democratization.

In conclusion, it should be noted that Uzbekistan's cooperation with developed countries during the years of independence has achieved great success with European countries in all areas, including cultural, humanitarian and trade-economic spheres and they will undoubtedly serve to bring it closer and develop it harmoniously.

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